

Design and Analysis of Robust School Platform

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Abstract:

Wooden platforms find extensive utility across diverse industries and environments owing to their multi-functionality, resilience, and aesthetic allure. Below are detailed explanations of their prevalent applications. The main objectives for the present work are defined based on gaps identified in the literature and the desired outcomes for the new ramp design. To investigate the influence of various parameters on the design of wooden platforms, a range of techniques has been utilized. These methodologies are further detailed in the subsequent discussion on the design of experiments (DOE) of 16 experiments. TOPSIS, one of the most widely used tool of MCDM is used for optimization of results obtained from ANSYS. Finally 15 mm thick with 3 supports is found optimal solution.

Introduction:

Wooden platforms have a wide range of uses across various industries and settings due to their versatility, durability, and aesthetic appeal. Here's an elaboration on some common applications:

Wooden platforms are frequently used in construction and building projects as scaffolding, flooring, or staging. They provide a stable surface for workers to stand on while working at heights, offering safety and convenience. Wooden platforms can also serve as temporary flooring during construction or renovation activities. In event planning and production, wooden platforms are often used as stages for performances, speeches, or presentations. They offer a sturdy and elevated surface for performers, speakers, or entertainers to engage with the audience. Wooden platforms can be customized in size and design to suit the specific requirements of different events. Wooden platforms are popular in outdoor settings such as parks, gardens, and waterfronts. They can be used as viewing platforms, picnic areas, or gathering spaces, providing visitors with a comfortable and elevated vantage point to enjoy the surroundings. Wooden platforms blend well with natural environments and can enhance the aesthetics of outdoor spaces. In retail environments, wooden platforms are often used for product displays, showcasing merchandise in an attractive and organized manner. Wooden platforms can create visual interest and add dimension to store layouts, drawing customers' attention to featured products or promotions. They are also commonly used in trade shows and exhibitions for displaying products or marketing materials. Wooden platforms can serve as elevated storage platforms or shelving units in warehouses, garages, or workshops. They provide additional storage space above ground level, helping to maximize storage capacity and keep items organized. Wooden platforms can be customized with shelves, compartments, or drawers to

accommodate different storage needs. In home improvement projects, wooden platforms are used for various purposes such as building decks, patios, or raised garden beds. They can also be used to create elevated seating areas, outdoor kitchens, or play structures in residential settings. Wooden platforms offer homeowners a versatile and customizable solution for enhancing their outdoor living spaces.

The usage of school wooden platforms spans across diverse activities and applications, offering a practical, versatile, and aesthetically pleasing solution for various needs ranging from construction and events to outdoor spaces and storage.

Literature review from previous research:

Many research works have been done in the field of school wooden platform. Following is the literature review of some papers giving more information about their school platform and wheel chair ramp

Arish Ibrahim *et.al* [1] reported that the manual wheel chairs are widely used because of its availability and economic factors. Even if it faces the limitation of accessing curbs and stairs. Some of the advanced electronic wheelchairs having the climbing feature but those wheel chairs are not affordable to common people and not suitable for daily usage in rough terrains. Author proposed a ramp attachment design that makes the normal wheelchair to climb the curbs on the streets and accessing the buildings without ramp facility. The design concept doesn't make any modifications in the basic design of wheelchair as it involves just an attachment of ramp and sliding mechanism. The proposed design can also applicable to shopping carts or any other people transferring devices for meeting the specific needs. Barbara Tewksbury *et.al* [2] focused on a pedagogical approach to geoscience education. Ramp is a teaching method developed by Tewksbury that emphasizes the importance of

engaging students in reading scientific literature and exploring real-world geological features, such as mountains, to enhance their understanding of earth science concepts. Phillip G Resor *et.al* [3] focused on a pedagogical approach to geoscience education. Ramp is a teaching method developed by Tewksbury that emphasizes the importance of engaging students in reading scientific literature and exploring real-world geological features, such as mountains, to enhance their understanding of earth science concepts. Jennifer M. Wenner *et.al* [4] outlined the rationale behind adopting ramp, in her teaching practices, highlighting the benefits it offers in terms of promoting active learning, critical thinking, and the application of theoretical knowledge to real-world geological scenarios. She

might describe specific instructional strategies and activities used to incorporate ramp into her courses, such as guided reading assignments, field trips, and hands-on investigations. Author discussed the outcomes and impacts of using ramp in the classroom, including its effects on student engagement, comprehension of geological concepts, and development of scientific skills.

Research Methodology:

The methodology for the robust design of an optimized school platform is designed to be systematic, comprehensive, and iterative, encompassing various phases from initial research to final validation. This approach ensures the creation of a school platform that not only meets but exceeds the needs and expectations of users.

Fig. Number

Literature Review and Objective Definition:

A thorough literature review is conducted to understand existing designs, materials, and considerations in wheelchair ramp construction. The main objectives for the present work are defined based on gaps identified in the literature and the desired outcomes for the new ramp design.

Research Framework Development:

A research framework is developed to guide the entire design process. This framework outlines key stages, methodologies, and deliverables.

Concept Generation and Selection:

Multiple design concepts are generated through brainstorming sessions, considering factors such as usability, portability, durability, and accessibility. These concepts are evaluated against

predetermined criteria to select the most promising design direction.

CAD Modeling and Simulation:

The selected design concept is translated into detailed CAD models, considering all relevant dimensions and features. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) simulations are performed using ANSYS software to assess structural integrity, load-bearing capacity, and overall performance under various conditions.

Experimental work:

To study the impact of different parameters on wooden platform design, a variety of techniques have been employed. These methods are elaborated upon in the subsequent point concerning the design of experiments (DOE). The capability of DOE aids

in process improvement by effectively screening factors to discern those crucial for elucidating process variation. Once these factors are identified, suitable tools facilitate comprehension of their interactions and influence on the design process. Subsequently, DOE can determine the optimal factor settings that yield the most effective design.

Design of Experiment:

Carefully planned experiments yield considerably more information and frequently demand fewer iterations compared to unplanned ones. Moreover, a meticulously designed experiment guarantees thorough evaluation of the

identified important effects.

Factors:

In this experimentation, factors are categorized into two groups: controllable and uncontrollable. The controllable factors include the thickness of the material and the number of central supports. The thickness of the material is varied from 12 mm to 25 mm, while the number of central supports encompasses four values ranging from none to three internal supports. . Accordingly, set the levels of the controllable variables:

- Thickness of Material : [12, 15, 18, 25]
- Number of Central Support : [0, 1, 2, 3]

Table Number 1

Ex. No.	Material thickness	Number of supports
1	12	0
2	12	1
3	12	2
4	12	3
5	15	0
6	15	1
7	15	2
8	15	3
9	19	0
10	19	1
11	19	2
12	19	3
13	25	0
14	25	1
15	25	2
16	25	3

Response Parameters:

With two controllable factors each having four levels, a total of 16 experiments are conducted, falling within the feasible range for a full factorial design. Models are constructed using Computer-Aided Design (CAD), and the resulting response parameters are documented as outputs. The response parameters are as below.

- ❖ Maximum Principal Stress
- ❖ Von-Misses or Equivalent Principal Stress
- ❖ Maximum Deformation
- ❖ Average Deformation
- ❖ Cost

The response parameters for all the experiments are recorded in the following table number 2

Table Number- 2 Experimental Reading

Ex. No	Max Principle Stress (N/Mm ²)	Equivalent Principle Stress (Pa)	Max. Deflection	Avg. Deformation	Cost
1	26043000	2550000000	0.974	0.039	2160
2	22789000	2250000000	0.924	0.035	2160
3	19636000	1890000000	0.916	0.031	2200
4	16282000	1590000000	0.918	0.02	2250
5	25502000	2500000000	0.874	0.029	2450
6	22670000	2220000000	0.824	0.025	2450
7	19839000	1920000000	0.616	0.021	2500
8	17070000	1690000000	0.418	0.01	2550
9	24020000	20037000	0.774	0.019	3280
10	21337000	1980000000	0.714	0.015	3280
11	18572000	17800000	0.614	0.011	3350
12	16007000	16800000	0.414	0.005	3400
13	22520000	2220000000	0.674	0.09	4300

14	21200000	2100000000	0.514	0.08	4300
15	17000000	1780000000	0.314	0.07	4350
16	14000000	1330000000	0.214	0.03	4400

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Optimization:-

Optimization entails identifying the optimal solution from a set of potential options to a given problem. It finds extensive application across various domains such as engineering, economics, and computer science, among others. Optimization aims to either maximize or minimize an objective function while adhering to specific constraints. The objective function represents the quantity to be maximized or minimized, such as profit, efficiency, or cost, while the constraints denote the limitations or conditions within which the optimization occurs. In this scenario, optimization is necessitated by the presence of five factors: maximum principal stress (in N/mm²), equivalent principal stress (in Pa), maximum deflection (in mm), average deformation

mm), and cost (in rupees). The goal is to minimize the values of all response parameters. Therefore, an optimization process is essential to achieve this objective.

MCDM, or Multiple Criteria Decision Making, addresses the challenge of decision-making in situations where multiple conflicting criteria must be taken into account. Real-world scenarios often involve balancing various objectives that may conflict with one another. MCDM offers methodologies and techniques to analyze, evaluate, and rank alternatives based on these multiple criteria. Initially, we aim to optimize the decision-making process using Overall Evaluation Criteria (OEC). The determined weightage factors are as follows:

Table Number 3 Weightage

Sr. No	MPS	Deformation	Cost
Case1	33	33	34
Case 2	25	25	50
Case 3	25	50	25
Case 4	50	25	25

Optimization by TOPSIS

Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution is a multi-criteria decision-making method used to determine the best alternative from a set of options based on multiple criteria. Here are the steps involved in TOPSIS:

Define Criteria and Alternatives: Identify the criteria (attributes) that will be used to evaluate the alternatives. Also, list the available alternatives that will be compared.

Normalize the Decision Matrix: Normalize the decision matrix to ensure that all criteria are on the same scale and to remove the influence of different measurement units. This is typically done by dividing each value in the matrix by the sum of squares of all values in the same column.

Determine Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix: Assign weights to each criterion based on their relative importance. Multiply each normalized value in the decision matrix by its corresponding weight to obtain the weighted normalized decision matrix.

Determine Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions: Identify the ideal solution (best performance for each criterion) and the negative-ideal solution (worst performance for each criterion) by taking the maximum and minimum values across all alternatives for each criterion, respectively.

Calculate the Distance of Each Alternative from the Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions: Calculate the Euclidean distance of each alternative from both the ideal and negative-ideal solutions. This distance

represents how similar each alternative is to the ideal or negative-ideal solution for each criterion.

Determine the Proximity to the Ideal Solution: For each alternative, calculate the relative proximity to the ideal solution by dividing the distance to the negative-ideal solution by the sum of distances to both the ideal and negative-ideal solutions.

Rank the Alternatives: Rank the alternatives based on their proximity to the ideal solution. The alternative with the highest proximity value is considered the most preferred solution.

Sensitivity Analysis (Optional): Conduct sensitivity analysis to assess the robustness of the results by evaluating how changes in criteria weights affect the ranking of alternatives.

By following these steps, TOPSIS provides a systematic approach for decision-making in situations involving multiple criteria and alternatives.

Imperial Case Study.

Now, let's delve into an imperial case study focusing on case1. The significance of imperial case studies lies in their capacity to offer depth, nuance, and context to our comprehension of imperialism and its enduring effects. By honing in on specific cases, researchers can unearth obscured histories, challenge prevailing narratives, and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the intricacies of imperialism. For the first case, the weightages are distributed as follows: 50% for Maximum Principal Stress, 25% for Maximum Deformation, and 25% for the remaining factor,

which is Cost. The values of Equivalent Principal Stress and Average Deformation exhibit a parallel trend to Maximum Principal Stress and Maximum Deformation, respectively. These normalized Matrix of all response factors—Maximum Principal Stress, Equivalent Principal Stress, and Cost—are tabulated in Table 4

Normalized Matrix:

To remove the influence of different measurement units, the decision matrix is normalized to ensure that all criteria are on the same scale. The same values are tabulated in table number 4

Table Number 4

EX. NO.	Deformation in meter	Equivalent Stress in Pa	Maximum Principle Stress in Pa	Average Deformation	Cost
1	0.344	0.307	0.316	0.237	0.169
2	0.327	0.258	0.277	0.212	0.169
3	0.324	0.217	0.239	0.188	0.172
4	0.325	0.342	0.198	0.121	0.176
5	0.309	0.303	0.310	0.176	0.192
6	0.291	0.262	0.275	0.152	0.192
7	0.218	0.231	0.241	0.127	0.195
8	0.148	0.003	0.207	0.061	0.199
9	0.274	0.270	0.292	0.117	0.256
10	0.252	0.002	0.259	0.091	0.256
11	0.217	0.002	0.226	0.067	0.262
12	0.146	0.303	0.195	0.030	0.266
13	0.238	0.287	0.274	0.546	0.336
14	0.182	0.243	0.258	0.485	0.336
15	0.111	0.182	0.207	0.425	0.340
16	0.076	0.000	0.170	0.182	0.344

Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix:

Each normalized value in the decision matrix is multiplied by its corresponding weight to

obtain the weighted normalized decision matrix. The table number 5 reflects the weighted normalized decision matrix.

Table Number 5

Ex. No	Deformation in meter	Maximum Principle Stress in Pa	Cost
1	0.08608	0.1582	0.0422
2	0.08166	0.1385	0.0422
3	0.08096	0.1193	0.0430
4	0.08113	0.0989	0.0440
5	0.07724	0.1549	0.0479
6	0.07283	0.1377	0.0479
7	0.05444	0.1205	0.0489
8	0.03694	0.1037	0.0498
9	0.06840	0.1459	0.0641
10	0.06310	0.1296	0.0641
11	0.05427	0.1128	0.0655
12	0.03659	0.0973	0.0665
13	0.05957	0.1368	0.0841
14	0.04543	0.1288	0.0841
15	0.02775	0.1033	0.0850
16	0.01891	0.0851	0.0860

Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions

Table Number 6

Expriment Number	Positive	Negative
1	0.07853	0.02424
2	0.06107	0.03159
3	0.04955	0.04574
4	0.04461	0.06362
5	0.07080	0.02083
6	0.05463	0.03067
7	0.03008	0.05226
8	0.01000	0.07525
9	0.06214	0.02166
10	0.04723	0.03676
11	0.03311	0.05544
12	0.02424	0.07853
13	0.06200	0.03835
14	0.05314	0.05318
15	0.04413	0.08226
16	0.04877	0.10123

Distance of Each Alternative from the Ideal and Negative-Ideal Solutions

Table Number 7

Expriment Number	Performance Score
1	0.235856552
2	0.340927622
3	0.479991433
4	0.587805376
5	0.227302547
6	0.35956557
7	0.634680782
8	0.882722125
9	0.258464235
10	0.437628227
11	0.626070089
12	0.764143448
13	0.382162329
14	0.500201785
15	0.650842715
16	0.674866369

Based on the analysis of the table, Experiment Number 8 (15 mm thick with 3 supports) emerges as the optimal solution for this set of weightages in the TOPSI for this case. A similar

procedure is conducted for the subsequent three criteria, and the outcomes are documented in Table Number 8

Table Number 8

Experiment Number	33-33-34	25-25-50	50-25-25	25-50-25
1	0.30	0.45	0.19	0.24
2	0.35	0.50	0.23	0.34
3	0.41	0.53	0.26	0.48
4	0.46	0.55	0.30	0.59
5	0.30	0.43	0.23	0.23
6	0.38	0.49	0.31	0.36
7	0.65	0.67	0.64	0.63
8	0.87	0.81	0.93	0.88
9	0.29	0.25	0.33	0.26
10	0.41	0.34	0.45	0.44

11	0.56	0.44	0.61	0.63
12	0.70	0.55	0.81	0.76
13	0.39	0.34	0.47	0.38
14	0.50	0.39	0.64	0.50
15	0.60	0.46	0.72	0.65
16	0.62	0.49	0.71	0.67

Figure Number 1

Conclusion:

To investigate the influence of controllable variable (thickness of material and number of central supports), CAD is used for modelling. DOE is formulated to find the number of experiments according to the number of controllable variables and its factors. Total 16 experiments has been designed and analyzed to find the response parameters. TOPSIS, one of the best tool of MCDM is used for optimization. The optimized parameters are explained through one in depth imperial case study.

The analysis from Table 8 and figure number 1 reveals that Experiment Number 8 (15 mm thick with 3 supports) emerges as the optimal solution for all cases. The conclusion draws toward Experiment Number 8, suggesting it as the superior solution overall. Experiment Number 8 (i.e. **15 mm thick with 3 supports**) is the best solution

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